

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

IMPROVING THE TECHNOLOGY OF MANUFACTURING TARTS FOR RESTAURANT ESTABLISHMENTS

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ABSTRACT

The article describes the technology of making special tarts for restaurants using coconut sugar.

Keywords: tarts, technology, restaurants, coconut sugar.

Formulation of the problem. A significant part of the diet of the modern population is flour confectionery products, which have already gained great importance in our lives, primarily due to their exquisite taste properties.

Confectionery flour products are high in calories due to the content of carbohydrates (starch, sugar), fats, and proteins. They include a number of minerals and vitamins of group B, PP, A. Today, the world market is at the stage of being filled with useful confectionery products, which will allow you to enjoy delicious products without harming your health. Ensuring the needs of the population in food products with reduced sucrose content is an urgent and timely problem for scientists and technologists.

Analysis of recent research and publications.

Flour confectionery products occupy a significant share in the total production of confectionery products and are presented in a wide range. Shortbread is called so because the products from it are crumbly. This is achieved due to the high content of sugar and fat in it, certain qualities of the flour and the peculiarities of the technological process [1].

The difficulty of replacing sugar in the production of food products, including flour confectionery, is related to its important technological functions. After all, sugar as a recipe ingredient, in addition to providing a sweet taste, significantly affects the course of the technological process, the formation of properties of semi-finished products, the structure and color of finished products. Therefore, when justifying the expediency and recommendations for the use of sugar substitutes in the manufacture of confectionery products, which differ in origin, composition, sweetness, etc., it is necessary to take into account their technological properties and the peculiarities of the groups of products for which they are intended [2,3].

Coconut sugar is a type of palm sugar obtained from the sap of the coconut tree. The production of coconut sugar is a two-step process. It begins with harvesting. Farmers cut a palm tree, and the palm sap begins to flow from it into bamboo containers. The juice is translucent and consists of 80% water. The collected

juice is then poured into larger vats (woks) and evaporated over low heat. When the water evaporates, the juice begins to turn into a thick syrup. Further, it can be used directly in this form, or subjected to further evaporation up to the transition to a solid state [4-6].

Solid coconut sugar is sold as blocks, soft paste or granulated sugar (fine crystalline sugar). Coconut sugar is moderately sweet, somewhat similar to cane sugar, but has a slightly different taste. The color, sweetness, and flavor of coconut sugar can vary depending on the type of coconut tree used, the season the sap was harvested, the location where it was harvested, and/or the method by which the sap was evaporated. Recently, the use of coconut sugar as a sweetener has become more common in developed countries [7-10].

The benefits of coconut sugar depend on the method of its production. It is extracted in the same way as birch sap. Next, the collected nectar is dried in the sun, as a result, it becomes like a thick syrup. In this form, it can already be used, since many manufacturers sell just syrup. In order to obtain crystalline granules, the syrup is well dried or frozen.

Coconut sugar contains a lot of substances necessary for the body, mainly vitamins B, PP, various minerals, amino acids. The calorie content of coconut sugar per 100 grams is 380 calories. Ordinary sugar is stripped of all its beneficial properties during processing, so it provides our body with only unnecessary calories. In addition, regular sugar has a high glycemic index and has a sickening, sweet taste. Unlike refined sugar, coconut sugar retains many useful substances and has a low glycemic index. It is equal to - 35.

The purpose of the work is the improvement of the technology of special tarts for restaurants by replacing white sugar with coconut sugar in the recipe.

Results.

A tart, less often a tart is an open cake with a filling inside that is not covered with dough. Usually the tart is made from shortcrust pastry. The filling can be sweet or savory, so the tart can be both a dessert and a main dish; although today it is common to make fruit tarts, which are sometimes filled with custard.

For the study, a tart was prepared according to a standard recipe, which was considered a control sample, and a tart was prepared according to an improved recipe, replacing white sugar with coconut sugar.

Table 1

Selection of recipe ingredients for a control sample of a tart	
Raw	Regulatory documentation
Wheat flour of the highest grade TM "Khutorok", Ukraine	DSTU 46.004-99. Wheat flour
White crystalline sugar PRIZMA-14 LLC, Ukraine	DSTU 4623:2006. White sugar. Specifications
Chicken eggs of the 1st category TM "Kvochka", Ukraine	DSTU 5028:2008. Chicken eggs are edible. Specifications
Butter De Luxe Foods & Goods Selected sour cream 82% fat, Germany	
Baking powder TM "Dobryk", Ukraine.	DSTU 2900:2006. Food concentrates. Technical conditions
Salt "Artemsil", Ukraine	DSTU 3583:2015 Table salt. Specifications
Apples are fresh «Red Chief».	DSTU 8133:2015 Fresh mid- and late-season apples. Specifications

Table 2

Selection of recipe ingredients for the researched tart sample	
Raw	Regulatory documentation
Wheat flour of the highest grade TM "Khutorok", Ukraine	DSTU 46.004-99. Wheat flour
Цукор кокосовий «VanaVita BIO», Таїланд	
Chicken eggs of the 1st category TM "Kvochka", Ukraine	DSTU 5028:2008. Chicken eggs are edible. Specifications
Butter De Luxe Foods & Goods Selected sour cream 82% fat, Germany	
Baking powder TM "Dobryk", Ukraine.	DSTU 2900:2006. Food concentrates. Technical conditions
Salt "Artemsil", Ukraine	DSTU 3583:2015 Table salt. Specifications
Apples are fresh «Red Chief».	DSTU 8133:2015 Fresh mid- and late-season apples. Specifications

Manufacturing technology. A machine method of making shortbread. Cut into pieces of butter with a uniform consistency are placed in the tanks of the whisking machine. Eggs (after initial processing) are mixed with salt, sugar, soda, ammonium and this mixture is gradually poured into the whipped fat in portions. Beat until the liquid is completely combined with the fatty mass and the sugar crystals disappear. If the egg mixture is quickly poured into the fat, the fat emulsion may separate. In this case, it is necessary to stop further preparation of the dough. The separated liquid must be drained, and the fat should be slightly heated with intensive stirring. Without stopping whisking, pour the strained liquid into the fat in small portions. Sifted flour is poured into the bowl of the dough kneading machine (7% of the flour is left for sprinkling), the whipped mass is transferred and the dough is kneaded for 1-2 minutes. The finished dough should have a soft, plastic consistency. You need to knead the dough quickly. An increase in the kneading time leads to a tightening of the dough, since the gluten of the flour swells more.

A manual method of making shortcrust pastry. Flour is sifted on the table in the form of a slide. Make an indentation in the center of the slide, put fat mixed with sugar into it, pour in the egg mixture and quickly knead the dough, starting from the base of the slide. The

finished dough after kneading should have a moisture content of 20% and a temperature not higher than 20°C.

The finished dough must first be collected into a lump, then rolled out a little with a rolling pin, put in a removable form, previously covered with parchment only on the bottom, and form the sides with the help of your fingers. The bottom of the base must be pricked with a fork to avoid unevenness during baking. Then we cover the dough with parchment, lay out some load and send it to bake for 20 minutes in the oven, the last 5 minutes should be baked without a load. The base for the tart must be completely baked to a golden color and ready.

To prepare apple jam, it is first necessary to carry out mechanical culinary processing of apples. After cleaning the apples, cut them into small cubes of 1.5*1.5 cm. Cover with water, add sugar and cook over low heat for 30 minutes. at a temperature of 80 degrees. Then add the rest of the sugar and continue cooking for another 60 minutes. Add pectin or corn starch previously diluted in a small amount of cold water. We brew the jam, pour it into a glass jar, close it with a lid and leave it until it cools completely.

The production of specialized products was carried out according to the traditional scheme. The introduction of additional raw materials was carried out at the stage of kneading the dough, while white sugar was

replaced by coconut sugar. This method made it possible to carry out the technological process without changing the main stages of preparation of the sand semi-finished product. The duration of kneading the shortbread is 20 minutes, the temperature of the dough is 19-24 °C. Then it was sent to cool in the refrigerator for 60 minutes. The molded sand base was baked at a temperature of 180°C for 18 minutes with the load, and another 5 minutes. without.

Apple jam was also prepared according to traditional technology, replacing white sugar with coconut sugar.

Tart preparation technology for small restaurants. Sanitize the eggs: soak in warm water for 10 minutes, then place the eggs in a 2% solution of perchloric lime for 5 minutes, then soak the eggs in a 2% solution of calcined salt and rinse with running cold water. Place cold butter, sifted flour, Jerusalem artichoke powder, turmeric and stevia in a deep container. Grind everything into fine crumbs and add a slightly beaten egg. Knead a homogeneous dough quickly. Wrap the dough in cling film and chill it in the refrigerator for 2 hours. We carry out mechanical culinary processing of apples: wash, peel, wash again under running water, cut and separate the stalk, core with seeds, wash and cut into

small cubes. Place chopped apples in a saucepan and add water, blanch for 10 minutes. Then add coconut sugar. Put the saucepan on a low heat, stirring occasionally for 20 minutes. Roll out the finished, cooled dough under two sheets of parchment paper, press out the bottom of the tart using a mold, cut off a strip 3 cm high and place it in the mold along the wall. Place in the refrigerator for 30 minutes. We heat the oven to 170°C. Take the mold out of the refrigerator, place it on a baking sheet, pierce the bottom with a fork and bake for 20-25 minutes. Place a glass on the prepared sand base to level the bottom of the tart. Fill the cooled sand base with apple jam and decorate with mint.

Organoleptic evaluation of the quality of finished products was carried out in accordance with DSTU 9799-74. The quality of the finished products was evaluated by the tasting committee on a five-point scale. The selection of samples for research was carried out in accordance with DSTU 5904 - "Confectionery products. Acceptance rules, methods of sample selection and preparation".

It was established that in terms of taste and aroma, tarts with coconut sugar received higher scores than the control sample prepared according to the standard recipe (Fig. 1.).

Fig. 1. Organoleptic assessment of tarts

Conclusions. Part of the nutritional substances of all groups of flour confectionery is represented by carbohydrates, among which a significant share is sugar. In connection with this, in world practice, scientists and industry specialists face the problem of finding alternative sources of raw sugar of natural origin. Researched and improved the technology of making tarts for special purpose restaurants, replacing white sugar with coconut sugar. It was established that in terms of taste and aroma, tarts with coconut sugar received higher scores than the control sample prepared according to the standard recipe.

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СИСТЕМА ОТСЛЕЖИВАНИЯ ПОДОЗРИТЕЛЬНЫХ ТРАНЗАКЦИЙ И АВТОМАТИЧЕСКОГО ОТЧЕТА О НИХ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В наши дни количество транзакций проходящих через системы платежей и банков достигает огромных масштабов. Далеко не все эти платежи являются для нас безопасными и приемлимыми. Поэтому необходимы регуляции направленные на отслеживание и мониторинг подозрительных транзакций, чтобы выявить проблемы и вовремя предотвратить их. Из-за количества транзакций и особенностей регуляций в какой-либо территориальной юрисдикции, неизбежно появляется необходимость в программном обеспечении, которое будет автоматизировать выполнение данных задач. В противном случае их выполнение не представляется возможным. В этой статье предлагается система отслеживания подозрительных транзакций с настраиваемыми параметрами, которая к тому же будет давать отчеты в выбранной форме, формате. Система предоставляет возможность настройки параметров для обнаружения подозрительных транзакций, которые могут варьироваться в зависимости от специфики бизнеса. Например, параметры могут включать в себя минимальную и максимальную сумму транзакции, местоположение и IP-адрес отправителя и получателя, тип транзакции и другие. Основной целью является сделать эту систему современной, быстрой и гибкой, чтобы соответствовать и подстраиваться под нужды бизнеса и законодательные требования определенной территориальной юрисдикции.

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, the number of transactions passing through payment systems and banks has reached enormous proportions. Not all of these payments are safe and acceptable for us. Therefore, regulations aimed at tracking and monitoring suspicious transactions are necessary to identify problems and prevent them in a timely manner. Due